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Conceptual Framework for Understanding Hate Speech

Work package 1 – Deliverable 1.1

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Lead beneficiary: Aarhus University

Authors: Matteo Melis, Benjamin Nangle, Tania Azadi & Leen d’Haenens

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents a conceptual and empirical framework for understanding hate speech within the context of the DEMINE project, contributing to the network's broader objective of addressing communication dynamics related to migration, polarisation, and social cohesion in Europe.

The report responds to a central challenge in hate speech research: the lack of conceptual clarity and consistency across disciplines, institutional contexts, and computational applications. It demonstrates that hate speech is not defined uniformly, but rather varies depending on normative, legal, and methodological assumptions. This variability has significant implications for research comparability, dataset construction, and the performance of automated detection systems.

To address this issue, the deliverable introduces a **modular conceptual framework** that decomposes hate speech definitions into a set of recurring "Conceptual Elements" (CEs). These elements capture core dimensions such as the communicative act, the target, the nature of harmful content, and the relation between hostility and attributed characteristics. The framework is organised into a layered taxonomy distinguishing foundational, extensive, and accessory elements, enabling transparent comparison and systematic construction of definitions across contexts.

The conceptual contribution is complemented by an **empirical assessment** using prompting-based experiments with large language models. By systematically varying definitional configurations, the study demonstrates that conceptual choices significantly influence automated hate speech classification outcomes. Importantly, these effects are model-dependent: the same definition may improve or degrade performance depending on the architecture, highlighting that definitions function as active components in computational systems rather than neutral descriptors.

In parallel, the deliverable includes a **scoping review of migration-related hate speech research**, based on a PRISMA-guided analysis of 582 studies, of which 255 focus specifically on content. The review identifies recurring discursive patterns, such as dehumanisation, threat framing, and "us-versus-them" narratives, as well as key actors involved in the production and dissemination of hate speech, including political actors, media institutions, online publics, and platform infrastructures.

The findings underline that hate speech emerges from a complex communicative ecosystem and is shaped by both discursive practices and structural conditions. Across studies, qualitative and discourse-analytical approaches dominate, with increasing integration of computational methods, reflecting a shift toward mixed-method research designs.

Overall, the deliverable advances DEMINE's research agenda by providing a structured and transparent framework for conceptualising hate speech across disciplines; empirical evidence of the operational consequences of definitional choices; and a comprehensive mapping of migration-related hate speech in contemporary scholarship.

The report concludes that improving conceptual transparency is essential for enhancing methodological rigour, comparability, and accountability in both research and applied contexts. It recommends that future work explicitly document definitional assumptions, align conceptual choices with normative and policy goals, and evaluate hate speech detection systems across diverse models and datasets.

2. About DEMINE

DEMINE goals

Globalisation and immigration have altered intercommunity relations, leading to a rise in intergroup conflict marked by discrimination against diverse minorities. This has given way to various forms of radicalisation and extremism, spanning religious, political, and xenophobic spectrums worldwide. Globalisation and immigration strain social cohesion (shared public values, group norms, guiding principles) in numerous countries. While individual attitudes may not have shifted significantly, the prominence of migration in public discourse and the polarisation of public opinion have increased substantially. As a result, a divided public opinion has become more overtly hostile towards migration.

The DEMINE (DEaling with conflicts related to MIgration: NEgotiating social cohesion through communication) European Joint Doctorate (DN-JD) network is a collaborative effort across disciplines. Its primary goal is to enhance Europe's capacity to address a significant challenge: the rise of various forms of radicalisation and extremism that pose a threat to social cohesion. Through a combination of inter-sectoral mobility and a balanced blend of research and transferable competences, DEMINE develops a much-needed framework on the role and interplay of interpersonal and mediated communication in intergroup relations and conflict related to migration and globalisation, ultimately contributing to social cohesion. DEMINE has crafted a comprehensive research and training programme to examine the complex relationships between various forms of communication, including traditional media, social media, and interpersonal interactions. This programme aims to understand how various communication channels shape individual attitudes and beliefs regarding migration, as well as their impact on intergroup dynamics (social cohesion), especially within the broader context of political and societal polarisation, and the processes of radicalisation, with a specific focus on migration-related aspects.

DEMINE Educational Goals

- Train nine doctoral candidates to become the next generation of interdisciplinary researchers skilled in digital methods, participatory community research, and the evaluation of intergroup conflicts.
- Equip candidates with advanced theoretical and practical knowledge, focusing on strategic analysis, community-based participatory youth work, and open-source intelligence techniques.
- Develop transferable skills such as self-management, inter-sectoral collaboration, and innovation-oriented thinking to prepare candidates for both academic and non-academic careers.
- Promote interdisciplinary and international mobility, enabling candidates to apply their research findings in real-world contexts and contribute to professional fields ranging from strategic analysis to media production.

DEMINE Research Goals

- Identify and analyse the differences and similarities across various forms of socially unacceptable, extreme discourse, particularly related to migration, at the intersections of politics, media, and interpersonal communication.
- Investigate the impact of extreme discourse on individual attitudes and beliefs, with a specific focus on adolescents and vulnerable populations, while understanding the socio-demographic and psychological factors influencing susceptibility.

- Develop countermeasures to empower adolescents, news media producers, and political actors to mitigate the societal impact of divisive discourse, fostering social cohesion and reinforcing democratic principles.
- Provide a nuanced, cross-cultural, and interdisciplinary understanding of the mechanisms of polarization and radicalization to inform effective strategies and policy interventions.

By integrating these educational and research goals, DEMINE aims to enhance Europe's capacity to address the growing societal challenges linked to migration, fostering resilience and inclusivity in an increasingly polarized world.

DEMINE Consortium

DEMINE consists of three academic partners namely, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Aarhus Universitet, and Università Degli Studi di Padova as well as nine non-academic partners including OCAM-OCAD, City of Mechelen, Textgain, The Migration Policy Group, Refugees Welcome, Institut for Menneskerettigheder, Stichting Bellingcat, Verwey-Jonker Institute, and Hannah Arendt Institute.

The DEMINE consortium will train nine doctoral candidates (DCs) within a cross-disciplinary and international environment, giving them the opportunity to network, study and collect data in Western, Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe (see secondments) in collaboration with academic and non-academic experts, with ample opportunities to develop transferable skills such as technology literacy, adaptability (i.e., not feeling helpless in the face of change), strong communication skills, and ability to work in a team, in a dependable and well-organised fashion.

3. Introduction

Hate speech has emerged as a central concern across a wide range of disciplines, such as sociology, communication studies, political science, ethics, computer science and law. The proliferation of online communication platforms has amplified both the visibility and the societal impact of harmful speech, raising urgent questions about democratic discourse, social cohesion, individual dignity and the limits of freedom of expression. As a result, hate speech has become the object of regulatory intervention, empirical investigation and technological mitigation strategies, particularly in the context of content moderation and automated detection systems (Tsesis, 2009; Kiritchenko et al., 2021).

Despite this shared concern, there is no consensus on what precisely constitutes hate speech. As is typical of complex social constructs, hate speech does not reflect a stable definition and is instead characterised by substantial ambiguity (Waseem & Hovy, 2016; Plaza-del-Arco et al., 2023). Definitions vary substantially across institutional, legal, academic and technical contexts. Some emphasise the protection of legally defined groups, others focus on communicative intent, harm, or social consequences, while still others conflate hate speech with broader categories such as offensive, abusive, or toxic language. This **definitional plurality** is not merely a terminological inconvenience: it directly affects the interoperability of datasets, the comparability of empirical findings, and the interpretability of computational models trained under divergent assumptions (Fortuna et al., 2020).

A particularly persistent source of confusion concerns the boundaries between **hate speech** and adjacent constructs such as **offensive language**, **abusive language** or **toxicity**. While these categories overlap in practice, they are conceptually distinct (Davidson et al., 2017; Waseem & Hovy, 2016). Offensive or abusive language may involve insults, profanity, or hostility without targeting a person or group based on socially salient characteristics, whereas hate speech is typically defined by the presence of hostility directed at individuals or groups because of who they are or are perceived to be. Failing to distinguish between these diverse constructs poses the risk of collapsing analytically different phenomena under a single label, leading to simplifying or ignoring their causes and their consequences.

This distinction is critical at a conceptual level. Conflating hate speech with general offensiveness weakens theoretical clarity and complicates normative debates about regulation and harm. From a legal and ethical perspective, hate speech is often treated as a more severe category, precisely because of its discriminatory dimension and its potential to legitimise exclusion or violence (Tsesis, 2002). Treating all forms of offensive expression as equivalent, therefore, risks either overextending regulatory frameworks or underestimating the specific harms associated with group-targeted hostility.

The importance of **conceptual clarity** becomes even more pronounced when definitions are operationalised in computational work. In Natural Language Processing (NLP) and related fields such as Computational Social Science (CSS), abstract concepts are translated into annotation guidelines, datasets, and classification labels. For instance, prior studies have shown that different operational definitions of hate speech can lead to substantially different model behaviours and performance outcomes, even when applied to the same underlying data (Ross et al., 2017; Roy et al., 2023). When hate speech is operationally defined in ways that blur its boundaries with offensive or abusive language, models trained on such data may learn proxies that prioritise surface-level cues (e.g., profanity or slurs) over the underlying relational and contextual features that characterise hate speech. This can result in systems that over-flag benign but impolite language, under-detect implicit or coded hate, or behave inconsistently across datasets that rely on different conceptual assumptions.

Moreover, inconsistent operational definitions hinder the comparability of computational studies. Models evaluated on datasets that encode different notions of hate speech may exhibit divergent performance patterns that reflect definitional differences rather than genuine model capabilities. Without explicit documentation of what conceptual components are included in a given definition, it becomes difficult to interpret results, assess bias, or transfer findings across domains. In this sense, conceptual ambiguity propagates downstream into technical artifacts, shaping both empirical outcomes and real-world deployment decisions.

Definitions of hate speech are not neutral descriptions of a phenomenon; they encode normative choices about what kinds of speech are considered harmful, who is protected, and which forms of harm are treated as socially salient. In computational research, it has been repeatedly shown that hate speech definitions vary substantially across datasets and studies, reflecting differing assumptions about protected characteristics, intent, severity, and harm (Waseem & Hovy, 2016; Davidson et al., 2017; Fortuna & Nunes, 2018). Decisions about whether to include implicit expressions, whether to require reference to protected characteristics, or whether to consider potential consequences all shape the form in which hate speech is presented and can modulate the boundary between hate speech and adjacent constructs such as offensive language or legitimate criticism (Fortuna et al., 2020; Plaza-del-Arco et al., 2023). Treating definitions as interchangeable obscures these choices and risks reifying conceptual inconsistencies in both research and practice.

Rather than advocating for a single, universal definition of hate speech, this report starts from the premise that **conceptual plurality** is, to some extent, inevitable and, to a certain degree, desirable. This is due to the social, cultural, and legal variability of the phenomenon. What is needed, however, is a shared **conceptual framework** that makes this plurality explicit, structured and transparent. Such a framework should allow researchers, practitioners and policymakers to articulate *how* a given definition is constructed, *which elements it includes or excludes*, and *why* these choices matter.

To address this need, this report presents **two contributions**. First, a **modular conceptual framework** for understanding hate speech, grounded in a systematic analysis of existing definitions drawn from academic research, institutional documents and platform policies. This framework is not only proposed at a theoretical level but is also empirically exercised by examining how different combinations of its conceptual elements function when instantiated as operational definitions in computational settings, specifically in a classification task. Second, this report includes a dedicated **scoping review of the literature on hate speech**, which surveys how the construct has been theorised, operationalized and debated across various disciplines. While the present section focuses on the development of the conceptual framework, the review of the literature provides broader contextual grounding and will be presented in a separate, dedicated part of the report.

The proposed framework decomposes hate speech definitions into a set of **Conceptual Elements (CEs)**. These distinct building blocks capture recurring dimensions of the construct, such as the form of communication, the target of the speech, the nature of the problematic content and the attributes on which hostility is based. These elements are organised into a multi-layer taxonomy that distinguishes foundational components from more specific or accessory aspects, including implicitness, exceptions and potential social or individual consequences (Melis et al., 2025).

This **modular approach** serves both descriptive and normative purposes. Descriptively, it provides a structured map of how hate speech has been defined across disciplines and contexts, highlighting points of convergence and divergence. Normatively, it encourages greater conceptual transparency by making explicit the assumptions embedded in operational definitions. Rather than replacing

existing definitions, the framework offers a scaffold for constructing, comparing and refining them in a principled way.

The relevance of such a framework extends beyond theoretical clarity. Conceptual elements can inform annotation guidelines, improve dataset documentation and support more interpretable and context-sensitive applications of automated detection systems. By making definitional choices explicit, the framework enables stakeholders to align methodological decisions more effectively with normative goals, whether these involve legal compliance, high recall moderation, protection against over-censorship or cross-cultural comparability.

A scoping review of the literature complements this framework by synthesising existing theoretical and empirical perspectives on hate speech across disciplines.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows. The **Methodology** section describes the process through which existing hate speech definitions were collected, analysed and decomposed into conceptual elements, as well as the criteria used to organise them into a coherent taxonomy. The **Results** section presents the resulting framework and illustrates how different combinations of conceptual elements yield distinct definitions with practical implications. Finally, the **Conclusion and Recommendations** section discusses how the framework can be applied across disciplines and offers guidance for researchers, practitioners and policymakers seeking to operationalise hate speech in a transparent and context-aware manner.

4. Methodology

This section illustrates the methodology employed to investigate how hate speech is conceptually defined and how such definitions function when operationalised in computational settings. The methodological approach is centered on the construction of a modular conceptual framework for hate speech, developed through a systematic analysis of existing definitions drawn from academic literature, institutional documents and platform policies. Rather than proposing a single authoritative definition, the methodology aims to decompose existing definitions into their constituent conceptual components and to organise these components into a transparent and reusable taxonomy.

In addition to its conceptual dimension, the methodology incorporates an **empirical** component that examines the operational implications of definitional choices. Specifically, selected configurations of Conceptual Elements derived from the framework are instantiated as natural language definitions and evaluated in prompting-based hate speech classification experiments using *large language models*. These experiments are designed as a methodological probe rather than as a benchmarking exercise to assess how variation in definitional structure influences automated classification behaviour under controlled conditions.

The methodology, therefore, combines three tightly connected components:

1. The qualitative identification and abstraction of Conceptual Elements from existing definitions;
2. The organisation of these elements into a multi-layer, modular taxonomy that distinguishes foundational, extensive and accessory components;
3. An empirical assessment of definitional variability through zero-shot prompting experiments conducted in a two-step design, which first refines core definitional components and then evaluates the effect of adding accessory elements.

Furthermore, this report includes a scoping review of scholarship on hate speech related to migration and ethnic minorities across disciplinary fields. The review maps how hate speech is conceptualised, operationalised, and examined in the literature, with particular attention to its linguistic and rhetorical characteristics and to the actors, institutions, and communication platforms involved in its production and dissemination. In doing so, the review provides an overview of how migration-related hate speech is defined and studied across relevant communicative contexts, including media, political communication, education, and social media. The scoping review addresses two research questions: (1) what types of hate speech are used to represent migration and ethnic minorities; and (2) who are identified as key producers or disseminators of such discourse. Studies were included when they examined migration-related hate speech, its defining linguistic or rhetorical features, or the actors responsible for producing or circulating it. Literature reviews, conference-only publications, non-English studies, research unrelated to human migration, and studies not addressing hate speech in a migration-related context were excluded.

The DEMINE scoping review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework to ensure a transparent and reproducible identification and screening process. A comprehensive literature search was conducted across three major bibliographic databases: EBSCO ($n = 423$), Scopus ($n = 1020$), and Web of Science ($n = 6803$). This search strategy resulted in a total of 8246 records identified for potential inclusion. Following aggregation of the retrieved references, duplicate entries were systematically removed ($n = 1097$), yielding a deduplicated dataset of 7149 unique records that proceeded to the subsequent screening stages. Following title- and abstract-level screening and full-text eligibility assessment, **582 full-text articles were retained and included in the DEMINE scoping review**, constituting the final evidence base of the study. Of these, **255** articles specifically focused on content, alongside studies addressing audience characteristics and interventions.

This structured reduction from broad database retrieval to a refined corpus of unique studies reflects the standard PRISMA trajectory and provides a transparent audit trail of the evidence-identification process. The PRISMA flow diagram included in the DEMINE documentation visualises each step of this progression, documenting the movement from initial identification through deduplication and preparing the dataset for title-abstract screening, full-text eligibility assessment, and final inclusion in the scoping review evidence base.

4.1 A Modular Conceptual Framework

Data Sources and Scope

The conceptual framework is grounded in a systematic collection of hate speech definitions drawn from heterogeneous but complementary sources. These include academic literature from computational linguistics, social sciences and legal scholarship; institutional and policy documents produced by international organisations and regulatory bodies; and platform-level definitions and moderation policies from major online services. In addition, a small number of definitions generated by large language models were included to reflect contemporary automated articulations of the construct.

The inclusion of these sources was motivated by the need to capture the diversity of contexts in which hate speech is defined and operationalised. Rather than privileging a single disciplinary or normative perspective, the goal was to identify recurring conceptual patterns across domains. The temporal scope of the collected definitions spans approximately two decades, with particular attention paid to definitions that have been explicitly operationalised in dataset construction, annotation guidelines, or content moderation practices, given their direct downstream implications (Melis M. et al., 2025).

Identifying Conceptual Elements of Hate Speech

The identification of Conceptual Elements (CEs) followed an inductive qualitative analysis of the collected hate speech definitions. Rather than assuming a predefined theoretical model, the analysis proceeded bottom-up, treating definitions as empirical artefacts that reflect how the construct of hate speech has been operationalised across disciplines and institutional contexts. Each definition was examined with the aim of uncovering the distinct conceptual components it mobilises to characterise hate speech.

The analysis involved systematically decomposing definitions into their constituent parts, focusing on *what kind of information* each definitional segment contributes. This included, for example, references to the communicative modality, the entity being targeted, the nature of the harmful or hostile content, and the basis on which hostility is expressed. Importantly, the analysis abstracted away from surface-level linguistic variation in wording to capture underlying conceptual functions shared across definitions, even when expressed using different terminology or stylistic conventions.

Through iterative comparison across definitions, recurring conceptual patterns were identified and progressively refined into a set of Conceptual Elements. These elements were defined as minimal but meaningful building blocks that encode distinct dimensions of the hate speech construct. Minimality was a guiding criterion: a Conceptual Element had to represent a unit of meaning that could not be further decomposed without losing conceptual specificity. At the same time, elements were required to be sufficiently general to recur across multiple definitions, rather than being idiosyncratic to a single source.

The identification process was guided by several analytical criteria. First, **conceptual necessity**: elements that appeared consistently across definitions and were required to distinguish hate speech from related phenomena were treated as foundational. Second, **explanatory relevance**: elements that provide further information on a Conceptual Element that are conceptually necessary. Third, **functional distinctiveness**: elements were retained if their presence or absence had implications for how hate speech is interpreted, operationalised or regulated, without altering its core meaning.

Frequency alone was not sufficient; some elements were included despite appearing in fewer definitions because they captured conceptually salient distinctions, such as implicitness or exceptions.

A central methodological concern during this process was avoiding circularity and overly context-dependent criteria. While many definitions rely on enumerations of protected groups to distinguish hate speech from offensive language, such lists vary across legal systems, cultures and institutions. Rather than treating protected-group membership as a defining element in itself, the analysis focused on more abstract relational components, such as the linkage between hostile content and attributed characteristics of a target, which remain applicable across contexts (Melis M. et al., 2025).

The resulting set of Conceptual Elements reflects both convergence and diversity in existing definitions. Some elements capture aspects that are nearly universal across definitions, while others encode optional or context-specific dimensions. Importantly, the elements are not intended to function as independent labels, but as components that acquire meaning through their combination. This compositional perspective allows definitions to vary in scope and emphasis while remaining analytically transparent about their underlying structure.

By explicitly decomposing definitions into Conceptual Elements, this methodological step provides the foundation for the subsequent taxonomy construction. It enables systematic comparison between definitions, clarifies how different conceptual choices shape operational definitions, and creates the conditions for analysing how such choices affect downstream empirical and computational applications.

Taxonomy Construction

Once the Conceptual Elements have been identified, they have been organised into a multi-layer taxonomy, according to their role within the hate speech definitions. The guiding principle of the taxonomy construction was that not all conceptual information contributes to a definition in the same way. Some elements are required to minimally distinguish hate speech from related forms of harmful or offensive communication, while others refine, contextualize, or qualify that core definition. To reflect this asymmetry, Conceptual Elements were grouped into layers based on their conceptual necessity and informational function.

At the core of the taxonomy, we collocate the **foundational elements** required to articulate a minimal and non-circular definition of hate speech and to distinguish it from adjacent constructs, such as offensive or abusive language. A second layer consists of elements that further specify or elaborate these foundational components, named as **extensive definitions** (of the CEs), by adding descriptive detail without introducing new conceptual dimensions. Finally, **accessory elements** capture additional aspects of hate speech that are not required for its basic identification but are nonetheless central in many definitions, such as references to implicitness, exceptions, or potential social and individual consequences. This layered organisation makes explicit which aspects of hate speech are considered essential and which are considered contingent or context dependent.

The taxonomy is intentionally **modular and compositional**. Conceptual Elements are not treated as fixed categories that must always co-occur, but as components that can be combined in different configurations to construct definitions with varying scope, granularity, and normative decisions. This design choice allows the taxonomy to accommodate legitimate variation across legal, institutional, and disciplinary contexts, while maintaining transparency about the conceptual assumptions underlying any given definition. By making these assumptions explicit, the taxonomy enables

systematic comparison between definitions and provides a structured basis for analysing how different conceptual choices affect both interpretation and operationalization (Melis M. et al., 2025).

Differentiation from Similar Constructs

A central methodological concern in the framework construction is the explicit differentiation between hate speech and adjacent constructs such as offensive language. Prior research has shown that these categories are frequently conflated in annotation practices and computational modelling, despite being conceptually distinct (Davidson et al., 2017; Waseem & Hovy, 2016).

Accordingly, the framework identifies specific Conceptual Elements that are required to distinguish hate speech from general offensiveness, most notably the explicit linkage between hostile content and attributes associated with a target group. Treating this distinction as a foundational requirement supports both theoretical clarity and more consistent operationalisation in empirical and computational work.

4.2 Operationalisation and Empirical Assessment via a Prompting Experiment

Although the primary aim of the proposed framework is conceptual, its development was informed by an empirical assessment of how different definitional choices affect downstream operationalisation in computational settings. To this end, the modular conceptual framework was employed in a series of prompting-based experiments designed to examine how varying combinations of Conceptual Elements influence automated hate speech classification.

The operationalisation process consisted of translating selected configurations of Conceptual Elements into natural language definitions of hate speech. Each definition corresponds to a specific combination of foundational, extensive, and accessory elements identified in the taxonomy. Importantly, the construction of these definitions followed a controlled design strategy: variations across definitions were limited strictly to the **conceptual content encoded by the Conceptual Elements**, while surface-level linguistic realisation (e.g., phrasing, syntactic structure, and stylistic choices) was kept as consistent as possible. This constraint was adopted to ensure that observed differences in model behaviour could be attributed to conceptual variation rather than to incidental wording effects (Melis et al., 2025).

The resulting definitions were embedded into prompts for **zero-shot hate speech classification**, a setting in which models are instructed to perform a task without exposure to labelled examples. Zero-shot prompting was chosen for two reasons. First, it reflects an increasingly common mode of deploying large language models in both research and applied moderation settings. Second, it allows the influence of definitional framing to be isolated, as model parameters, training data, and task structure remain fixed while only the definition of the target construct varies.

Models and Datasets

The prompting experiments were conducted using three instruction-tuned large language models drawn from different model families: **Meta-LLaMA-3-8B-Instruct**, **Mistral-7B-Instruct**, and **Flan-T5-XL**. These models were selected to represent contemporary open-weight architectures with differing pretraining and instruction-tuning strategies, allowing an assessment of whether definitional effects generalize across model types (Melis et al., 2025).

Evaluation was performed on three widely used hate speech datasets, each representing a different type of data and annotation strategy. **HateCheck** (Röttger et al., 2021) is a synthetic, functionality-driven test suite designed to probe specific types of hate speech phenomena. **Learning from the Worst (LFTW)** (Vidgen et al., 2021) is a human-in-the-loop dataset curated to include challenging and borderline cases. **Measuring Hate Speech (MHS)** (Sachdeva et al., 2022) consists of real-world social media content annotated using a measurement-theoretic approach. Together, these datasets provide complementary perspectives on hate speech, ranging from controlled test cases to naturally occurring instances.

Two-Step Experimental Design

The experiments followed a **two-step design** aimed at systematically exploring the role of definitional detail and conceptual composition.

In the first step, the analysis focused on refining the **Hate Speech Base** definition by examining which *extensive specifications* of the foundational Conceptual Elements provided the most informative operationalization. Specifically, definitions were constructed by selectively enriching the foundational elements with more detailed descriptions of the form of communication, the target or the nature of the problematic content. This step assessed how increasing definitional specificity within the core structure of hate speech affects classification behaviour.

In the second step, the best-performing definition from the first phase was further augmented with **accessory Conceptual Elements**, such as references to implicit hate speech, explicit exceptions, lists of addressed attributes, and potential social or individual consequences. This step was designed to evaluate how adding qualitatively different types of conceptual information influences model sensitivity, particularly in borderline or ambiguous cases.

Across both steps, the experimental setup was controlled such that the same models, datasets, and task instructions were used, while only the conceptual composition of the definition included in the prompt was varied. This design isolates the impact of definitional choices from other sources of variation.

Model outputs were evaluated using standard classification metrics, with additional analyses focusing on error distributions, including false positives and false negatives. Particular attention was paid to how different Conceptual Elements affected sensitivity to implicit hate speech, misleading non-hateful content, and offensive but non-hateful language.

The results show that definitional choices encoded through Conceptual Elements can lead to systematic and sometimes substantial differences in classification behaviour. In some cases, more detailed definitions reduced false negatives by improving sensitivity to nuanced or implicit forms of hate speech; in others, they primarily reduced false positives by clarifying what should not be classified as hate speech. Importantly, these effects varied across models, indicating that definitional sensitivity interacts with model architecture rather than producing uniform outcomes (Melis et al., 2025).

These experiments are not interpreted as identifying an optimal or universally correct definition of hate speech. Instead, they serve as empirical evidence supporting the central methodological claim of this report: **conceptual choices in defining hate speech are consequential when operationalised in automated systems**. Even when models and data are held constant, differences in definitional structure can materially shape detection outcomes. As such, the prompting experiments function as

a methodological validation of the modular conceptual framework and underscore the importance of conceptual transparency in both research and applied moderation contexts.

4.3 Scoping Review of Hate Speech Research

The scoping review identifies several recurring **conceptual elements** through which hate speech is used to represent migration and ethnic minorities across the analysed studies. First, hate speech frequently relies on **dehumanisation and disgust metaphors**, depicting migrants as contaminating, invasive, or less than human, thereby legitimising exclusionary imaginaries and harsh bordering practices (e.g., Jenks & Bhatia, 2020; Okoye, 2022). Second, a prominent element concerns **threat and securitising representations**, in which migrants and refugees are framed as dangers to public safety, social order, or national stability (e.g., Dib & Sandy, 2023; Gorman & Culcasi, 2021). Closely related are **criminalisation and illegality frames**, where associations with violence, disorder, or unlawful presence function rhetorically to deny legitimacy and rights (Dib & Sandy, 2023; Mayaleh et al., 2024). Third, the literature highlights **Islamophobic and racialised constructions**, portraying Muslims or groups associated with Islam through suspicion, radicalisation tropes, and civilisational antagonism (e.g., Fuentes-Lara & Arcila-Calderón, 2023; Gorman & Culcasi, 2021; Figueux & Van Gorp, 2022). Fourth, hate speech often mobilises **us-versus-them othering and nationalist or populist blame**, establishing symbolic boundaries and moral hierarchies of deservingness between majority populations and migrants (Okoye, 2022; Shah, 2024). Fifth, several studies document **conspiracy- and disinformation-inflected hostility**, in which misleading narratives and conspiratorial claims intensify polarisation around migration (Okoye, 2022; Dutta, 2025). Finally, hate speech may be conveyed through **humour, irony, memes, or ridicule**, enabling the normalisation of derogatory meanings while preserving plausible deniability (Figueux & Van Gorp, 2022; Shah, 2024). Taken together, these elements demonstrate that migration-related hate speech operates through a limited yet recurrent repertoire of discursive constructions that combine dehumanisation, threat framing, boundary-making, and mediated normalisation.

The scoping review identifies several recurring **actor-related conceptual elements** associated with the production and dissemination of migration-related hate speech. First, **political actors and partisan campaign environments** emerge as central producers of exclusionary and boundary-drawing rhetoric, where anti-immigration narratives are mobilised for agenda-setting, legitimation, and electoral positioning (e.g., Gorman & Culcasi, 2021; Jenks & Bhatia, 2020). Second, **news media organisations and journalistic outputs** constitute important sites of circulation and amplification. Through framing practices, selection routines, and narrative structuring, media coverage may reproduce hostile categorisations or reinforce threat-oriented representations of migrants and ethnic minorities (e.g., Okoye, 2022; Dib & Sandy, 2023; Bodrunova & Smoliarova, 2022). Third, the literature highlights the role of **online publics and user-generated participation**, including commenters, platform users, and networked audiences who actively produce, reinterpret, and diffuse hostile discourse within interactive digital environments (Jenks & Bhatia, 2020; Shah, 2024). Fourth, several studies point to **organised ideological or extremist actors**, such as right-wing extremist networks, that strategically disseminate migration-related hostility through coordinated communication practices in digital spaces (Masalha & Bas, 2023). Finally, dissemination is shaped by **platform infrastructures and affordances**, particularly major social media environments that structure visibility, engagement, and algorithmic circulation of hate-laden narratives (Fuentes-Lara & Arcila-Calderón, 2023; Shah, 2024; Dutta, 2025). Taken together, these findings indicate that migration-related hate speech is not attributable to a single source but rather emerges from an interconnected communicative ecology in which political

actors, media institutions, online publics, organised networks, and platform infrastructures interact to produce and circulate hostile discourse.

The studies included in the scoping review display a set of converging methodological features that characterise current research on migration-related hate speech. Coding strategies are predominantly manual or hybrid qualitative approaches, typically embedded in discourse-analytical traditions. Several contributions combine interpretive manual coding with computational or AI-assisted procedures, indicating a gradual methodological shift towards mixed analytical pipelines. Abductive and interpretivist orientations are also evident, particularly in studies examining social media discourse or multimodal communicative forms.

Across the corpus, the primary units of analysis consist of textual and discursive artefacts, including news articles, magazine coverage, and a wide range of social media content such as posts, comments, hashtags and other forms of user-generated communication. In some cases, the analytical focus extends beyond individual texts to encompass accounts, actors, or even platform-level and cross-platform discourse environments, reflecting an ecosystemic understanding of how hate speech circulates within contemporary communication infrastructures.

Common analytical dimensions centre on the degree of hostility and dehumanisation expressed in discourse, processes of boundary construction such as “us versus them” distinctions, calls to action or mobilisation, and framing strategies that portray migrants and ethnic minorities in terms of threat, danger, or illegitimacy. Taken together, these dimensions reveal a shared concern with the ways hate speech produces moral hierarchies, legitimises exclusion, and contributes to securitising narratives.

The analysed studies are typically situated within salient social and political contexts marked by conflict or heightened public attention. These include the aftermath of terrorist attacks, the political and media dynamics surrounding Brexit and broader European migration debates, national migration policy developments, and episodes of communal or political violence. This pattern indicates that migration-related hate speech is most often examined during periods of intensified political tension and societal contestation. Geographically, the dataset demonstrates an international yet uneven distribution of research. European contexts, such as Belgium, the United Kingdom, and cross-national European settings, are particularly prominent, alongside studies situated in African and Middle Eastern regions, including North African national contexts such as Morocco. Overall, this distribution suggests a Eurocentric but nonetheless transregional orientation in the existing literature. In terms of study design, most contributions can be characterised as content or discourse analyses, frequently qualitative or mixed-method in nature. Although ethnographic and computational approaches appear in a smaller subset of studies, the dominant methodological paradigm remains interpretive and discourse-focused, underscoring the centrality of meaning-making processes in the analysis of migration-related hate speech.

5. Results: Conceptual Framework and Empirical Prompting Experiments

This section reports the results of the modular conceptual framework and its empirical instantiation through prompting-based experiments. The results are presented along two tightly connected dimensions: (i) conceptual results concerning the structure and composition of hate speech definitions, and (ii) empirical results showing how definitional choices encoded through Conceptual Elements affect automated classification outcomes across models and datasets.

Conceptual Results: Structure and Composition of Hate Speech Definitions

The conceptual analysis shows that hate speech definitions can be seen as a systematically compositional construct. Across academic, institutional, and platform sources, definitions consistently rely on a set of recurring Conceptual Elements that jointly encode the discriminatory and relational nature of hate speech. These elements include the presence of a communicative act, the identification of a target, the articulation of problematic or hostile content, and the explicit linkage between such content and attributes associated with the target.

A central outcome of the conceptual analysis is the formulation of a layered structure among Conceptual Elements. Foundational elements form the minimal conceptual core required to distinguish hate speech from adjacent constructs such as offensive or abusive language. Extensive elements refine this core by providing more detailed descriptions of communicative form, target specification, or content type, while accessory elements introduce additional conceptual dimensions, including implicitness, exceptions, addressed attributes, and potential social or individual consequences.

This layered organisation proposes a structure to work with hate speech definitions that differ in **scope and emphasis**, while keeping stable the core elements, rather than using fundamentally incompatible conceptions. Aiming to use definitions that appear divergent, but in reality, share the same foundational structure, but differ in whether and how extensive they are, or which/how many accessory elements are included. The framework, therefore, enables systematic comparison between definitions and a method to use more standardized hate speech definitions.

Empirical Results: Effects of Definitional Choices on Classification Outcomes

The empirical results provide insights that definitional choices encoded through Conceptual Elements have measurable effects when operationalised in zero-shot hate speech classification, though these effects are strongly model-dependent. Across all experiments, varying the conceptual composition of the definition included in the prompt led to consistent shifts in classification behavior; however, the magnitude and direction of these shifts differed substantially across model architectures. Even when models, datasets, and task formulations were held constant, the same definitional modification could improve performance for one model while degrading it for another, indicating that definitional framing interacts with model-specific inductive biases rather than producing uniform effects.

These findings confirm that definitions are not neutral task descriptions, but active components that shape how automated systems interpret and classify content. Moreover, they demonstrate that conceptual transparency, while necessary for interpretability, is not sufficient to guarantee consistent outcomes across models. Instead, the operational impact of a definition depends jointly on its conceptual structure and on the characteristics of the model that instantiates it, reinforcing the need to evaluate definitional choices across multiple architectures rather than assuming portability of results.

The two-step experimental design reveals that models respond differently to different types of definitional information. In the first step, which focused on **refining the Hate Speech Base (HSB)** through extensive definitions of foundational elements, performance patterns varied substantially across model architectures. Flan-T5 exhibited a clear positive relationship between definitional informativeness and classification performance, showing consistent improvements as definitions became more detailed. This trend was reflected both in higher macro-F1 scores and in a positive correlation between definition length and performance across datasets. In contrast, Llama-3 and

Mistral did not benefit from increasingly detailed base definitions, with Llama-3 in some cases performing best without any explicit definition at all, likely due to dataset exposure during pretraining.

The second experimental step, which introduced **accessory Conceptual Elements** such as implicit hate speech, exceptions, lists of addressed attributes, and possible implications, further highlighted the model-dependent nature of definitional sensitivity. Mistral emerged as the model most responsive to this additional conceptual information, showing consistent performance gains across datasets when accessory elements were added, particularly combinations involving implicit hate and possible implications. In several cases, Mistral's performance in this step surpassed not only its own baseline but also the best-performing definitions from the first step. Flan-T5, by contrast, showed little to no additional improvement in the second step, despite remaining consistently above its no-definition baseline, while Llama-3 benefited only sporadically from accessory elements and only on specific datasets.

These differences are not merely quantitative but reflect qualitatively distinct classification strategies. Error analyses reveal that Llama-3 tends toward a conservative strategy that reduces false negatives at the cost of increased false positives, particularly when definitions are added to the prompt. Mistral, in contrast, shows the opposite tendency, frequently misclassifying hate speech as non-hateful content unless provided with more specific conceptual guidance. Flan-T5 maintains a comparatively balanced error profile but exhibits higher false negative rates on challenging, human-in-the-loop data, suggesting a more cautious interpretive stance overall.

The fine-grained analysis of HateCheck functionalities further demonstrates that Conceptual Elements do not affect all types of hate speech uniformly. Models struggled most with counter-speech and misleading non-hate content across all conditions, indicating a strong reliance on surface-level lexical cues. However, adding **exceptions** to the definition reduced errors in misleading non-hate cases, while explicitly specifying **implicit hate speech** improved performance on classes involving coded, ironic, or indirect expressions. These effects were especially pronounced for Mistral, the only model to show consistent gains from accessory elements in the second experimental step, reinforcing the conclusion that certain architectures are particularly sensitive to targeted conceptual clarifications.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that definitional effects are **systematic but not universal**. All models are sensitive to definitional framing, but they respond to different kinds of conceptual information in different ways. Some architectures benefit primarily from increased descriptive detail in foundational elements, while others respond more strongly to accessory elements that clarify edge cases or normative boundaries. As a result, the same definition can improve performance for one model while degrading it for another, and no single definitional configuration emerges as optimal across models and datasets.

The empirical results, therefore, reinforce the central conclusion of the study: **definitions of hate speech are consequential artifacts** whose effects depend on both their internal conceptual structure and the characteristics of the models that operationalise them. Conceptual transparency is necessary to interpret model behavior, but it does not eliminate the need for empirical validation. Instead, the modular framework provides a principled way to explore, document, and reason about these interactions, enabling more informed and context-sensitive deployment of automated hate speech detection systems.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

This report has addressed a central challenge in the study and operationalisation of hate speech: the absence of a shared, transparent, and analytically robust way of reasoning about definitions across

disciplines, institutional contexts, and computational applications. Rather than proposing a single authoritative definition, the report introduced a modular conceptual framework that decomposes hate speech definitions into recurring Conceptual Elements and organises them into a structured taxonomy. This approach makes explicit the conceptual assumptions that underlie different definitions and clarifies how definitional choices shape both interpretation and operationalisation.

The conceptual analysis demonstrates that hate speech is best understood as a systematically compositional construct. Across academic, institutional and platform-based sources, definitions share a common foundational structure while differing in how they specify, extend, or qualify that structure. By distinguishing between foundational, extensive, and accessory Conceptual Elements, the framework reveals that many apparent disagreements between definitions stem not from incompatible understandings of hate speech, but from differences in scope, emphasis and normative orientation. Making these differences explicit enables more principled comparison between definitions and reduces conceptual ambiguity.

The empirical assessment further reinforces the importance of this framework. When instantiated as natural language definitions in prompting-based classification experiments, different configurations of Conceptual Elements led to systematic and sometimes substantial differences in automated hate speech detection outcomes. Crucially, these effects were shown to be **model-dependent**: the same definitional modification could improve performance for one model while degrading it for another. This finding highlights that definitional choices interact with model architectures and inductive biases, rather than producing uniform operational effects.

Together, the conceptual and empirical results support a key conclusion of this report: **definitions of hate speech are consequential artifacts**. They shape annotation practices, dataset behaviour, model evaluation, and ultimately the real-world deployment of moderation systems. Treating definitions as interchangeable or leaving them under-specified risks obscuring these effects and undermining the comparability, accountability, and interpretability of research and applied tools.

Based on these findings, the following **recommendations** are offered to support more transparent, robust, and context-aware approaches to the study and operationalisation of hate speech.

For interdisciplinary research, definitions of hate speech should be treated as explicit methodological choices rather than implicit background assumptions. Researchers are encouraged to document the conceptual composition of the definitions they use, specifying which Conceptual Elements are included, how they are specified, and which are intentionally excluded. Adopting a modular perspective can improve comparability across studies and facilitate dialogue between disciplines that approach hate speech from different normative and methodological standpoints.

For dataset development and annotation, annotation guidelines should be grounded in clearly articulated Conceptual Elements rather than relying solely on broad labels or examples. Dataset documentation should explicitly state how hate speech is distinguished from adjacent constructs such as offensive or abusive language, and which conceptual criteria guide annotation decisions. This would support more transparent dataset reuse and reduce the risk of unintentional conceptual drift when datasets are applied in new contexts.

For computational modelling and evaluation, definitional choices should be systematically evaluated across multiple model architectures. Given the demonstrated model-dependent effects, performance results obtained under a single definitional framing or with a single model should not be assumed to generalise. Evaluation protocols should account for how conceptual framing influences model

behaviour, particularly with respect to trade-offs between false positives and false negatives and sensitivity to implicit or borderline cases.

For policy and content moderation contexts, the framework highlights the importance of aligning definitional choices with normative goals. Definitions designed to maximise coverage may prioritize sensitivity to implicit or indirect hate speech, while definitions aimed at minimising over-censorship may emphasise stricter foundational criteria and explicit exceptions. Making these trade-offs explicit can support more accountable moderation practices and clearer communication between policymakers, platforms, and affected communities.

More broadly, the modular conceptual framework presented in this report provides a shared vocabulary for reasoning about hate speech definitions and their consequences. It does not seek to replace existing definitions, but to make them more transparent, comparable and empirically examinable. By linking conceptual structure to operational outcomes, the framework supports more responsible and reflexive approaches to the analysis and governance of hate speech in digital communication environments.

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The conceptual framework and empirical analyses summarised in this report are grounded in prior research reported in Melis et al. (2025), which provides the full description of data sources, experimental setup, prompting strategies, model configurations, quantitative results and extended analyses. The present report focuses on conceptual synthesis and interpretation and does not reproduce all technical details or results in full.

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